

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

**Learning for Democracy
and Civic Action:**
An Educators' Guide

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www.CriticalChangeLab.eu

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Critical ChangeLab consortium

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1 Introduction

Critical ChangeLab was a Horizon Europe research and innovation project (2023 - 2026) which engaged young people (aged 11 - 18) in creative approaches to democracy and civic education in 10 European countries. Through this participatory research, we explored issues that mattered to the participating young people, and developed responsive and youth-centred methodologies and approaches that can be used by educators in schools and other educational settings like youth clubs, museums, libraries, makerspaces or summer camps.

The Critical ChangeLab approach to democratic pedagogy aims to:

- **Promote youth autonomy and agency**, nurturing young people's capacity to make informed decisions and take purposeful action in their communities
- **Foster active participation**, creating opportunities for learners to collaboratively engage in democratic processes and public life
- **Strengthen individuals' confidence** to interact in democratic contexts, helping them develop the knowledge, values, attitudes, and skills necessary for constructive dialogue, negotiation, and collective problem solving
- **Support social inclusion**, by cultivating competences that help learners recognize and challenge discrimination, promote human dignity, and engage respectfully across differences
- **Encourage lifelong learning**, particularly through education for democracy that unfolds across formal, non-formal, and informal learning environments

About this guide

This guide outlines the pedagogical model developed through this research, so that educators may run their own Critical ChangeLabs with young people. A Critical ChangeLab is a flexible, participatory learning process that helps participants to explore real-world issues that affect their lives and communities, think critically about democracy and power, and take actions towards positive change. Rather than delivering fixed content or curricula, the approach centres on dialogue, collaboration, creativity, and action. Students are encouraged to ask questions, share experiences, and learn with and from one another.

Critical ChangeLabs work especially well within Global Citizenship Education or Civic Education and related subjects, as they connect local experiences with wider social, political, and global issues. The process supports students to examine inequality, challenge misinformation, and imagine fairer futures, while building skills such as critical thinking, empathy, collaboration, and active participation. Topics are chosen together with students and can be adapted to different age groups, timeframes, and curriculum contexts.

Possible starter topics for student groups include:

- Inequality in everyday life (e.g. education, housing, gender, race, disability, or migration)

- The rise of far-right ideas and how they spread online and offline
- Misinformation and disinformation on social media and its impact on democracy
- Technology, data, and power (e.g. surveillance, algorithms, AI, digital exclusion)
- Climate justice and who is most affected by environmental change
- Young people's voices in decision-making at school, local, or national level
- Media representation and whose stories are heard or ignored
- Belonging, identity, and exclusion in diverse societies
- Redesigning urban or rural environments to be more inclusive and sustainable – considering climate resilience, access to public space, and the needs of both human and more-than-human communities

These topics are starting points rather than fixed themes. Students are encouraged to refine them, connect them to their own experiences, and explore the questions that matter most to them.

2 Pedagogical Approach

The Critical ChangeLab learning process is organised into five main phases:

1. **Grounding** – getting started and establishing shared understanding.
2. **Co-Constructing Knowledge** – exploring ideas and learning from each other.
3. **Envisioning** – imagining new possibilities or solutions.
4. **Putting into practice** – trying things out.
5. **Reflecting together** – looking back and learning from the experience.

These phases are similar to approaches many teachers already know, such as inquiry-based or project-based learning. The key idea they all share is that learners play an active role: their curiosity, motivation, and choices drive the learning.

Although the process follows these phases, it is **flexible rather than step-by-step**. Phases can overlap or be revisited if needed. It is especially important to start with *Grounding*, so everyone understands the purpose and approach, and to end with *Reflecting together*, which helps learners make sense of what they have done. Moving from one phase to the next should depend on when participants feel ready, not on a fixed schedule.

Critical ChangeLabs are based on the idea that **democracy is learned by doing**. This means giving learners enough time to work together meaningfully. Longer or repeated sessions allow trust to grow, ideas to develop, and reflection to happen. This deeper engagement helps learners practise collaboration, shared decision-making, and respect for different perspectives.

Facilitation in Critical ChangeLabs focuses on **active participation and collaboration**. The facilitator's role is to support open dialogue, make the process clear and inclusive, and ensure that everyone has a voice. The aim is to create a learning space that feels shared rather than top-down.

Figure 1. Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy

2.2 Grounding

Figure 2. Participants working together during the grounding session of a Critical Changelab (Critical Changelab: European Alternatives)

The **Grounding phase** helps set up the group for working well together. It introduces the purpose of the Critical ChangeLab and focuses on everyday democracy, while also covering practical matters. The main aim is to help participants feel comfortable, connected, and ready to work together.

This phase builds trust, sets shared expectations, and creates a sense of purpose before moving into deeper exploration. A key goal is to create a **safe and inclusive space** where everyone feels confident to speak, ask questions, and take part.

Key elements of the Grounding phase:

- **Introduce the process:** Participants get to know each other and understand why they are there. They share their interests, motivations, and expectations. Facilitators are open about their role and goals, helping create an atmosphere of openness rather than authority.
- **Create a safe space together:** The group agrees on what makes the space respectful and welcoming. This includes shared values, ways of listening, and how to handle disagreements. Agreeing on these rules together sets a positive tone for the work ahead.

2.3 Co-constructing Knowledge

Figure 3. Youth taking part in a Critical Changelab organized during the Ars Electronica Festival 2025 (Critical Changelab: Ars Electronica)

In this phase, participants **decide together what the Lab will focus on** and start exploring the topic in depth. The emphasis is on issues that matter in young people's everyday lives, especially where there are tensions, challenges, or disagreements.

Participants build understanding together by sharing experiences, asking questions, and looking at different viewpoints. The aim is not to give ready-made answers, but to help learners think critically about democracy, power, and fairness.

Key elements of co-constructing knowledge:

- **Co-define the topic:** The group agrees on the main theme of the Lab, ensuring everyone feels ownership of it.
- **Start from personal experience:** Participants connect the topic to their own lives. These real experiences make complex ideas easier to understand and discuss.
- **Explore different perspectives:** Learners look beyond their own views by engaging with other voices, information, or creative inputs (such as media, guest speakers, or visits).
- **Look at power and inequality:** Together, the group examines what shapes the issue – who has power, who doesn't, and why – linking personal experiences to wider social patterns.

2.4 Envisioning

Figure 4. Future news created by youth participating in a Critical Changelab (Critical Changelab: Trinity College Dublin)

The **Envisioning phase** is about imagination and possibility. Participants are encouraged to think beyond “how things are” and explore “what could be.” They question assumptions and experiment with bold or unusual ideas about the future. This phase helps learners understand that the future is not fixed – it is shaped by choices made in the present. Imagining alternatives is treated as an important skill for creating change.

Key elements of envisioning:

- **Link past, present, and future:** Participants explore how past experiences, current situations, and future hopes are connected.
- **Use ‘What if?’ thinking:** Learners create speculative ideas or scenarios that challenge existing ways of thinking and highlight hidden assumptions.

- **Imagine alternatives:** The group develops ideas for fairer, more sustainable ways of living and organising society, reinforcing the idea that change is possible.

2.5 Putting into Practice

Figure 5. Theatre play ideated by participants of a Critical Changelab in Lesvos, Greece (Critical Changelab: LATRA).

This phase focuses on **turning ideas into action**. Participants work together to test out their ideas through practical activities, small projects, or creative interventions. The emphasis is on learning by doing. Actions can be small and local, but they help show what change can look like in real life. Importantly, this phase values experimentation – trying things out, learning from mistakes, and adapting ideas.

Key elements of putting into practice:

- **Design and prototype:** Participants create and test ideas, such as campaigns, artworks, events, or other small-scale actions.
- **Share and discuss:** Ideas are shared with others through presentations, performances, or discussions. Feedback helps participants improve their ideas and learn together.

2.6 Reflecting Together

Figure 6. AI Ambassador Program participants reflecting on their experiences during the lab (Critical Changelab: University of Oulu)

Reflection runs **throughout the whole process**, not just at the end. It helps participants think about what they are learning, how they are working together, and how their thinking is changing. Reflection is done together and supports democratic skills like listening, openness, and shared decision-making. It helps participants recognise progress, deal with challenges, and plan what comes next.

Key elements of reflecting together:

- **Keep reviewing:** Regular check-ins help the group notice what is working, what feels unclear, and what might need adjusting.
- **Reflect together at the end:** Participants look back on the whole experience, share insights, and recognise learning and effort.
- **Decide next steps:** The group agrees on what to do next — this might be personal actions, sharing ideas with others, or continuing the work in future sessions.

3 Methods

The Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy draws on practices from (i) Arts and design, (ii) Futures, (iii) Dialogical learning, (iv) Participatory research and (v) Community engagement. These are introduced briefly and illustrated with selected examples - full descriptions of these methods and how to apply them in a classroom setting can be accessed at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18778048>

3.1 Arts and Design Methods

At the Labs, visual, narrative, performative, and maker-based methods help participants explore different ways of knowing and understanding the world. These creative practices also offer forms of expression beyond text or speech, making participation more accessible and inclusive. Below are some examples of methods we use at the Labs.

Visual

- **Collage:** Artistic technique where different materials—such as photographs, paper, fabric, or digital elements—are combined and layered onto a single surface to create a unified composition about a particular issue.
- **Drawing and sketching:** Production of images by hand, using lines and shapes to represent ideas, objects, or scenes.
- **Mapping:** Graphic representation of aspects such as emotions, concepts or relations.

Figure 7. Participants mapping interests by creating filter bubble mood boards. (Critical ChangeLab: Waag)

Figure 8. Advocacy posters created by using collage technique (Critical Changelab: Tactical Tech)

Figure 9. Local and refugee children collaborate in a mixed-group creative workshop using drawing, role-play, and storytelling to explore justice and inclusion (Critical Changelab: LATRA)

Narrative

- **Memes:** Production of funny or relatable pictures, videos, or text that share an idea or joke people can easily understand and spread online.
- **Podcasts:** Creation of an audio show that people can listen to online or download, usually released in episodes covering different topics or stories.
- **Zines:** Elaboration of self-published booklets by participants.

Figure 10. Participants working on their podcast episodes in the recording studio at the Ars Electronica Center (Critical Changelab: Ars Electronica)

Figure 11. Zine about food waste created by one of the participants (Critical Changelab: Institute for Social Research in Zagreb)

Performative

- **Image Theatre:** Participants use their bodies to create still images that represent ideas, emotions, or situations, often as a way to explore and discuss them.
- **Role Play:** Interactive exercises where participants act out characters or situations to practice skills, explore ideas, or address problems in a realistic way.
- **Theatre of the Oppressed:** Performative method in which participants act out a local issue engaging with the audience in testing and discussing different solutions.

Figure 12. Participants producing their videos (Critical Changelab: European Alternatives)

Design and maker-based

- **Brainstorming and Rapid Ideation:** Fast idea generation activity to foster participants' creativity
- **3D Modelling:** Process of creating three-dimensional objects or scenes on a computer, allowing them to be viewed and explored from any angle.
- **Prototyping:** Building simple models or versions of a product or idea to test how they work before making the final version.

Figure 13. Participants sketching their artifact on paper before creating it in Inkscape and laser-cutting it (Critical Changelab: University of Oulu)

Figure 14. Examples of games created by participants (Critical Changelab: Waag)

Figure 15. Participants involved in 3D modelling (Critical Changelab: Kersnikova)

3.2 Futures

Futures-oriented methods are powerful tools for helping young people reimagine democracy and work toward more desirable futures. Below is a selection of examples:

- **Design fiction:** Design practice to explore and criticise possible futures through provocative scenarios narrated through designed artifacts.
- **Futures Scenarios:** Generation of visions about futures through narration and storytelling.
- **Futures Triangle:** Method for mapping temporal competing factors on a specific issue: the pull of the future, the push of the present, and the weight of history
- **Futures Wheel:** visual brainstorming tool that maps out the possible direct and indirect consequences of a trend, event, or decision in a circular diagram to explore its ripple effects into the future.
- **Historical Analysis through Timelines:** Creation of temporal representations to explore the evolution of a given issue.

- **Speculative Design:** Design practice oriented the critical exploration of various futures about complex issues.

Figure 16. Design output of imagining the most unjust school (Critical Changelab: University of Barcelona)

Figure 17. Participants envisioning preferable future scenarios using the futures triangle method (Critical Changelab: University of Oulu)

3.3 Dialogic and Discursive Approaches

Approaches based on dialogue and open discussion help participants create shared understanding through conversation and diverse viewpoints. Below are some examples of methods used at the Labs:

- **Fishbowl Discussion:** conversation format where a small group talks in an inner circle while others observe from an outer circle, and participants can rotate between listening and speaking roles.

- **Five Whys Analysis:** Small group discussions using the “5 Whys” method to explore root causes of an issue and brainstorm potential solutions.
- **Structured Discussions:** guided conversation where participants follow clear rules, roles, or steps to ensure focused, balanced, and purposeful dialogue on a specific topic.
- **Walking Debate:** Participants express their stance on a given issue by moving around the room

Figure 18. 5whys? – identifying causes and consequences of throwing away food (Critical Changelab: Institute for Social Research in Zagreb)

3.4 Participatory Research

At the Labs, young people take part as co-researchers, actively helping to shape the research questions, methods, and results. Below are some techniques used to support their participation in the research activities:

- **Collective Ethnography:** collaborative research method where a group jointly observes, documents, and interprets cultural or social practices to build shared understanding from multiple perspectives.
- **Community Mapping:** participants create visual maps to identify local resources, challenges, and relationships within their environment.
- **Photovoice:** observation-based visual method in which youth use photographs to document their experiences, perspectives, and concerns.

Figure 19. Example of a future scenario where participants envisioned the worst city for young people to live in (Critical Changelab: Trinity College Dublin)

3.5 Community Engagement

Building relationships with local communities helps young people expand their understanding of societal challenges and identify opportunities to take action. You can support these connections through the following activities:

- **Experts' Interventions:** external specialists share knowledge, insights, or guidance to deepen understanding and enrich discussion on a specific topic.
- **Field Visits:** experiential learning method where participants go to real-world settings to observe, interact, and connect theory with practice through direct experience.
- **Participation in Cultural Events:** experiential method where participants engage with art and cultural activities to reflect, interpret, and connect creative expression with learning.
- **Sharing Opinions with External Stakeholders:** Youth present their views to experts and politically influential stakeholders for open discussion and debate.

Figure 20. Visit to the Red Cross' food bank to experience real world solutions to food waste (Critical Changelab: Institute for Social Research in Zagreb)

Given that every Critical ChangeLab is different, based on theme, context and other constraints, the methods listed in this table do not map rigidly to different phases of the Critical ChangeLab Model. Instead, methods should be selected for each phase based on the intended outcome, and the suitability of the method for the context of the lab.

4 Additional Resources

4.1 Tools to Support Growth

For individuals:

MOOC Youth, democracy and technology: participatory approaches for critical consciousness, offered by University of Oulu

<https://digicampus.fi/course/view.php?id=5919>

This online free course helps you learn practical ways to support young people in shaping democratic life both online and offline. Drawing on the ideas of Paulo Freire, bell hooks, and Henry Giroux, the course introduces hands-on methods, case studies, and creative tools for strengthening critical literacy, digital rights awareness, eco-social justice thinking, and participatory use of technology. Designed for teachers, youth workers, activists, and students, it offers flexible online study through seven themed modules, interactive resources, and activities you can apply directly in your work. Upon completion, you can earn 2 ECTS credits and/or a digital learning badge. The course is open to everyone, free of charge, and available in English.

For organizations:

Democracy Health Questionnaire for Non-Formal Educational Institutions and Schools

<https://zenodo.org/records/13767190>

This questionnaire is designed as a self-assessment tool for organisations that offer formal or nonformal education. It helps you reflect on how well your institution supports democratic practices today and identify areas to strengthen in the future. It is available in ten European languages: English, Catalan, Croatian, Dutch, Finnish, French, German, Greek, Slovenian, and Spanish.

4.2 Project Repositories

You can find more information about the Critical ChangeLab project—and the materials created through it—in the following channels:

Project website: criticalchangelab.eu

Zenodo library: <https://zenodo.org/communities/cclab>

5 About

5.1 Critical ChangeLab in Ireland

Critical ChangeLab in Ireland was led by the [School of Education, Trinity College Dublin](#)

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

While the EU-funded stage of the Critical ChangeLab project is now complete, to discuss developing and implementing a Critical ChangeLab in your educational context, please contact Dr. Mairéad Hurley: mairead.hurley@tcd.ie

We would like to see the approach used and shared widely to promote democratic empowerment among young people in Ireland.

5.2 Critical ChangeLab Consortium

The Critical ChangeLab consortium brought together organisations across Europe united by a commitment to strengthening democratic culture and empowering young people. The consortium's shared mission was to support youth in reimagining and shaping the future of democracy through creative, critical, and participatory practices.

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